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The Human Corona-virus Circulation in the USA, 2019-2020

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Abstract

Coronavirus was never expected to become an international issue. However, the virus has managed to spread from China, where the first outbreak was reported to the United States. Despite reassurances from leaders and other officials, the virus is continually going out of hand. The possibility of the virus being spread by mosquitoes is even more threatening. There is a need to conduct more research to identify the best methods of containing the condition before it becomes a global pandemic.

Keywords: Coronavirus, Usa, Covid-19, Circulation, 2019-2020

Nobody could have thought the human coronavirus would turn out to be an international tragedy. During its onset, many people thought it was just another fever. However, as it advanced and became life-threatening, people were shocked. But, even with the first reported deaths, there was still no cause for concern. All that needed to be done was to quarantine the first identified cases and keep the virus from spreading further. However, despite the best efforts of governments, the CDC, and other health research institutions, the disease has spread from China to the United States. This article evaluates the circulation of human coronavirus from 2019 to 2020.

Coronavirus starts to like the regular flu, which has symptoms that show cv-19 (Szczepanski et al., 2019). This is according to questionnaire services from 10 patients studied between December 2019 and February 2020. CDC reports project that the cv-19, in 2019, was is yet to arrive in the United States. Yet in 2020, field measurements show that the disease has been in the country for over a year. Following interviews with ten patients, most surviving patients report that they get sick with a symptom that attacks their nervous system for about two weeks.

One of the patients reported that the doctor informed him on January 23 that he had just the regular flu.

One of the patients reported that the doctor informed him on January 23 that he had just the regular flu. He had been in contact with many people in a given venue. Considering he had been healthy before and

had never needed to take any medication other than Aspirin at most once a year, he was surprised at how the regular flu could keep him down for so long. Since January 23, he had been sick for about two weeks and could not even leave his room. According to the patient, this particular flu makes the patient feel organ shutdown, sore and dry throat, and the body feels dry (Perlman & Zhao, 2013). The next day, the patient develops a fever, and the sore throat dissipates only to return any time. The patients have to forfeit the company of their loved ones once they confirm that they might be infected with the coronavirus.

Figure 1. Map of the U.S. showing the states that have been affected by a coronavirus (Livescience, 2020)

The outbreak of coronavirus began in Wuhan, China. The first case of the virus in the United States was announced by federal health officials on January 20 the year 2020 (CNN, 2020, March 9). The individual who was confirmed to have the virus had just come back from Wuhan, China, to Washington and had spent only five days in the country. The announcement came as a shock to many people, and many travels

were affected.

At that time, the largest outbreak of the virus beyond the borders of mainland China was on a cruise ship that had been floating in Japanese waters (Bloomberg, 2020). It was announced that the Diamond Princess was carrying more than 700 passengers who had been infected with the coronavirus. The cruise ship had been docked at Yokohama since February 4, and in it were more than 3600 people, 428 of them being Americans. With the reports of the virus, none of them was allowed to leave the ship.

By February 25, federal health official gave a warning that there were high chances that the virus would spread in the U.S. According to Dr. Nancy Messonnier, the director the National Center for Immunization and Respiratory Diseases at CDC, it was not a question of whether the virus would spread in the country, but when it would happen, and the number of people would end up with severe illnesses (CNN, 2020). By then, it had been confirmed that the virus had entered the United States and would only continue to spread.

There was also no evidence to prove that he had traveled recently, thereby exposing himself to the virus.

It did not take long before someone in the United States died from the coronavirus. On February 29, a patient who had coronavirus in Washington State succumbed to the disease. It was the first reported fatality arising from the virus in the country. The deceased was a man in his 50s and had other health conditions as well, and no evidence proved that he had come into close contact with a person who is infected. There was also no evidence to prove that he had traveled recently, thereby exposing himself to the virus. Researchers are still examining how he got infected with the virus.

Even before the first fatality from the virus in the United States had been fully understood, yet another state in the U.S. reported its first case of the disease. On March 1, New York City reported its first confirmed case of the disease (Reuters Editorial, 2020). It was reported that the patient got in contact with the deadly disease in Iran (CNN, 2020). Governor Andrew Cuomo stated that there was no cause for anxiety since the risk level for the virus in the state was generally low. However, the issue is continually running out of hand. As can be seen on the map in Figure 1, the virus has spread to over ten states and is

continuing.

Come March 4, yet another person died from the disease in Northern California, who became the first person to die from the virus out of Washington state. He was an elderly man who had other health problems and probably got exposed to the virus when he had traveled onboard Princess Cruises, which had voyaged in February from San Francisco to Mexico (Livescience, 2020). On that same day, a ship from Hawaii was held off the coast of California, suspecting that they might be infected, thereby locking out more than 3500 people from reaching their destinations. The ship, Grand Princess, had previously carried the passenger who was the first to die of coronavirus in California. No passenger was allowed to leave until after the test results were out. Twenty-one positive coronavirus cases were later confirmed by the officials.

Without a vaccine for the virus, this disease could become a world pandemic.

On March 6, authorities in Florida announced the death of two coronavirus patients in the state. These were the first deaths that were perceived to have any link to the one on the East Coast. More than 12 cases were also confirmed by the state, which is considered to be the second-largest cluster on the East Coast (CNN, 2020). The largest of them was recorded in New York.

The U.S. cases of coronavirus are now more than 500, and 70 of those are repatriated to the United States (as of 31.03.2020, there are 183,875 cases while 3,720 deaths). Twenty-one of those people is still on board the Grand Princess, which has been in limbo since March 4. The ship is expected to head for Oakland, California, once the tests have been completed. The cases are being reported at new places at an alarming rate, a nursing home in Washington being the hardest hit. Life Care Center nursing home has reported at least 16 fatalities from the virus.

As if the quick rate at which the disease is spreading is not enough, the other transmission methods are projected to arise. Research specialists speculate that by summer, the virus could be spread by mosquitoes. If this happens, the deadly virus will become as common as Malaria. Without a vaccine for the virus, this disease could become a world pandemic. There is a need for more research on the disease to come up with a preventive medication like an immunization.

Otherwise, this could just be the end of the world as we know it, at least for the humans.

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